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DESENVOLVIMENTO DEMOGRÁFICO DE ASSENTAMENTOS RURAIS DEMOGRAPHIC DEVELOPMENT OF RURAL SETTLEMENTS DESARROLLO DEMOGRÁFICO DE LOS ASENTAMIENTOS RURALES

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Área Temática: Demographic Trends, Macroeconomic Effects, and Forecasts.

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Resumo: A pesquisa trata da definição de tendências modernas e direções prioritárias de regulação estatal do desenvolvimento demográfico dos assentamentos rurais da Ucrânia e do Brasil no contexto dos processos de transformação social.

Investigar exaustivamente a dinâmica populacional a longo prazo, a composição sexual e etária da população nas áreas rurais, analisar tendências em fertilidade e mortalidade em áreas rurais e mudanças estruturais recentes nesses processos. As características modernas do movimento migratório dos residentes rurais, bem como são consideradas as especificidades da formação da composição socioeconômica da população do meio rural.

A necessidade de consideração sistemática do impacto dos principais fatores no potencial demográfico dos assentamentos rurais e na formação da política estadual, são determinados mecanismos e instrumentos para a sua regulação.

Palavras-chave: áreas rurais, desenvolvimento demográfico; potencial; regulamentação governamental.

Abstract: The research deals with the definition of modern trends and priority directions of state regulation of demographic development of rural settlements of Ukraine and Brazil in the context of social transformation processes.

Comprehensively investigate the long-term population dynamics and sex and age composition of the population in rural areas, analyse trends in fertility and mortality in rural areas, recent structural changes in these processes. The modern features of the migratory movement of rural residents, as well as the specifics of the formation of the socio-economic composition of the population in rural areas are considered.

The necessity for systematic consideration of the impact of the main factors on the demographic potential in rural settlements and the formation of state policy, mechanisms and instruments for its regulation are determined.

Key-words: rural areas; demographic development; potential; government regulation.

Resumen: La investigación trata de la definición de las tendencias modernas y las direcciones prioritarias de la regulación estatal del desarrollo demográfico de los asentamientos rurales de Ucrania y Brasil en el contexto de los procesos de transformación social.

Investigar exhaustivamente la dinámica poblacional a largo plazo y la composición por sexo y edad de la población en las zonas rurales, analizar las tendencias de la fertilidad y la mortalidad en las zonas rurales, cambios estructurales recientes en estos procesos. Se consideran las características

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modernas del movimiento migratorio de los residentes rurales, así como las características específicas de la formación de la composición socioeconómica de la población en las zonas rurales.

La necesidad de una consideración sistemática del impacto de los principales factores sobre el potencial demográfico en los asentamientos rurales y la formación de la política estatal, mechanisms and instruments for its regulation are determined.

Palabras-clave: zonas rurales; desarrollo demográfico; potencial; regulación gubernamental

Introdução.

The purpose of the research is to determine modern trends and priority directions of state regulation of demographic development of rural settlements of Ukraine and Brazil in the context of social transformation processes.

The subject of the analysis will be demographic changes (mainly the process of depopulation, aging of the population, foreign migration), improvement of living conditions (equipping households with elements of technical infrastructure, access to public services, transport accessibility), analysis of the deagrarianisation process (decreasing role of agricultural livelihoods rural areas, as well as employment in agriculture), analysis of the non-agricultural sector (the non-agricultural labor market for the rural areas inhabitants) and the agricultural sector (changes in the agrarian structure) and the characteristics of the labor market situation in rural areas (employment, unemployment).

At the same time, there are many new problems of rural areas, which include problems related to unemployment, a spectrum of social problems inherent in the current state of development of the Ukrainian countryside; problems of a methodical and organizational nature, connected, first of all, with the lack of reliable information about various aspects of the functioning of rural areas under the condition of the transformation of the socio-economic system and the imperfection of the methodology of studying these problems, etc. Therefore, there is an urgent need to study the level of social development of rural areas of Ukraine and Brazil, its demographic potential, to develop research technologies for comprehensive analysis of the conditions of rural areas.

Procedimentos Adotados.

Analyzing the demographic potential of rural areas in the context of social transformation processes, it is necessary to emphasize that the size of the population, especially that part of it that is engaged in the production process, is a decisive factor in the socio-economic development of the country, therefore, demographic problems should be subject to proper theoretical understanding, constant macro-level monitoring and to be decided at the level of strategic state priorities. A clear understanding of the socio-demographic characteristics of the population, problems and prospects for their development is extremely important for forecasting and planning effective social policy of the state. Preservation of the population and improvement of its qualitative characteristics can be one of the strategic directions for the state. In this case, minimization of social risks, which are the factors of formation of demographic losses, are recognized as a component of the policy of ensuring national interests. Under such conditions, the positive socio-demographic structure of the population makes it possible to ensure the protection of the main spheres of national security and, accordingly, to ensure their sustainable development. (Malynovska, 2021).

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Resultados e discussão.

Socio-demographic risks are inertial in nature, and therefore are the most strategically dangerous, as they irreversibly deform the structure of society. Socio-demographic processes in the village of Ukraine have their own specific characteristics, due to several factors. Beginning in 1991, the main factor in the continuous reduction of the rural population is depopulation. Depopulation has become a fundamental factor in the acceleration of the aging population, which is the most significant feature of long-term changes in its gender and age composition. The load on the working age population as persons of working age and after-working age in villages is significantly higher than in cities and from normative indicators. A characteristic feature of the migration situation in the countryside is the constant predominance of the outflow of population over the arrivals. Because of the long-term outflow of young people, the reduction of its demographic and labour potential was due to the loss of the most productive in the demographic and economic terms of the population.

Migration movement is also added to the decline of the rural population: domestic, interregional and interstate, which is an accurate indicator of the economic and social situation in the country. It has been established that migration plays a dominant role in the formation of human resources, which in recent years has been intensively developed and considered by us as the main cause of the social decline of the peasantry, the main destructive force of the demographic basis of its social rebirth.

While studying the socio-demographic problems of the Ukrainian village, many economists focus not only on quantitative changes in the indicators of demographic development, but also on the factors that shape them. Thus, a study of the correlation between the average annual number of workers in agriculture and the indicators of the volumes of migration flows has confirmed the increase of the link between the reduction in employment in the field and the processes of leaving the village. Almost complete functional connection is observed between the coefficients of arrival in rural areas and employment in the countryside.

International demographic statistics pay close attention to the assessment of the age composition of the population, since regardless of the level of research (global, regional and international), the age distribution of residents is closely related to the problems of the labor market, the state of consumption and a number of other vital issues.

When studying the socio-demographic problems of the Ukrainian countryside, many economists focus not only on quantitative changes in demographic development indicators, but also on the factors that shape them. Thus, studies of the correlation between the average annual number of employees in agriculture and the indicators of the volume of migration flows (in the coefficients of arrival and departure) of different directions and levels at the beginning of the current century confirmed the strengthening of the connection between the reduction of employees in the industry and the processes of leaving the countryside, in particular in interregional and intra-regional flows. An almost complete functional relationship is observed between the coefficients of arrival in rural areas and rural employment. (*Kurylo, 2023*).

Among the global problems of humanity that need to be taken into account when drawing up a development strategy for both the country and its regions, special attention should be paid to those that lie in the social plane. These include, in particular, the problems of ensuring demographic security, which are characterized by a negative balance of natural population growth and high infant mortality compared to developed countries of the world, and the problems of population

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depopulation, which are characterized by low birth rates and high mortality, as well as a high degree of demographic burden of the disabled population to workable.

The conceptual idea of building a system of indicators for assessing the level of demographic safety is to combine the study of the main demographic processes (natural and mechanical reproduction of the population), the structural characteristics of the population, as well as qualitative parameters from which to separate the health of the population and the spread of socially dangerous diseases. The developed system of indicators of demographic security is important as an effective tool for preventing critical situations and achieving the goals of safe development. (Gogol, 2018).

Considerações Finais.

The main mechanism of demographic development is the development and implementation of targeted programs for solving individual problems. Need to be taken into account when developing a strategy for the development of both the country and its regions to assess the state of demographic security system of indicators. It is necessary to develop not only threshold values, which are the beginning of negative destructive changes in the demographic system, but also target benchmarks that represent the strategic goals of individual components of demographic security.

In order to find the best models, it is advisable to take into account the experience of foreign countries and develop their own set of instruments in the field of state regulation of demographic processes in accordance with the defined goals and priorities of demographic development. The conceptual approach, which provides for the separation of the state regulation of the sphere of development of rural areas, will make it possible to direct resources to solve the socio-demographic problems of the rural areas.

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